

MANAGEMENT OF THE TEACHING CAREER: CONCEPTUAL, NORMATIVE, AND STRATEGIC PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The teaching career is shaped as a complex professional trajectory, characterized by a set of essential components that define the identity, competencies, and responsibilities of teachers within the educational system. Continuous evaluation and professional development constitute fundamental pillars in the advancement of the teaching career. In 2025, the teaching profession in Romania underwent significant legislative, normative, and procedural changes. The stages of professional progression from entry into the profession to the assumption of leadership, mentoring, or supervisory roles are regulated by a specific legislative framework and are closely linked to periodic performance evaluation, the attainment of teaching degrees, and active participation in continuous professional development. The teacher becomes a central actor in the process of educational modernization, and the professionalization of the teaching career represents a key prerequisite for improving the quality of education. The

professionalization of the teaching career is a complex and dynamic process through which educational activity is recognized, strengthened, and developed as a profession defined by clear standards of competence, responsibility, and autonomy. In the contemporary context of social, economic, and technological transformations, this process entails a shift from a traditional, knowledge-transmission approach to a reflective and adaptive one, in which the teacher becomes a facilitator of learning, a cultural mediator, and an agent of change. The alignment between the personal and institutional dimensions of the teaching career, which can contribute to the creation of a modern educational system based on competence, motivation, and lifelong learning, can be achieved through effective teaching career management. The present article proposes a theoretical study based on the analysis of strategic documents and regulations issued by the Ministry of Education regarding the development of the teaching career.

Keywords: professional teaching career, educational reform, educational legislation, professionalization of the teaching career, management of the teaching career.

1. The Teaching Career and Its Defining Elements

The Education Law, in conjunction with the related normative acts, establishes the official framework governing the organization and functioning of the teaching career, delineates its constitutive stages, and enshrines the teaching career as a structured, progressive, and evolutionary professional trajectory.

The teaching career represents the ensemble of professional stages, activities, and responsibilities assumed by an individual engaged in educational activity within the education system, beginning with initial training, continuing with entry into the profession, professional development through the attainment of teaching degrees, and extending to the holding of leadership, guidance, or supervisory positions in the field of education. It is thus shaped as a complex

professional pathway, characterized by a series of essential components that define the identity, competencies, and responsibilities of the teaching staff within the educational system. The fundamental elements of the teaching career are structured as follows:

- Initial Teacher Education and Continuous Professional Development (CPD) – Initial teacher education involves the completion of secondary or higher education programmes in the subject area corresponding to the disciplines taught, supplemented by psycho-pedagogical training delivered through accredited teacher education departments (Departments for Teacher Training – DPPD). This initial preparation is subsequently strengthened through continuous professional development (CPD), which includes participation in in-service training courses, postgraduate programmes, master’s and doctoral studies, as well as other forms of professional learning, aimed at ensuring adaptation to evolving educational requirements and the dynamics of contemporary society.

- Teaching Activity – Teaching activity involves the implementation of the instructional and educational process within educational institutions, aiming at the transmission of knowledge, the development of competencies, and the cultivation of students’ critical thinking. Assessment constitutes an essential component of this process, encompassing the application of appropriate methods and tools to measure academic progress and to guide future educational interventions.

- Career Progression through the Attainment of Teaching Ranks – The teaching career is structured into professional advancement stages that reflect the level of competence, experience, and commitment to educational practice. These stages include: novice, certified teacher, Teaching Rank II, and Teaching Rank I. Advancement to each level requires the fulfillment of rigorous conditions, including the accumulation of professional experience, successful completion of

inspections and specialized examinations, as well as the preparation of a methodological-scientific paper.

- Adherence to Ethical and Legal Standards – Professionalism within the teaching career entails the adoption of exemplary ethical conduct, in accordance with the values and norms specific to the profession. Compliance with the legal framework, institutional regulations, and deontological principles contributes to maintaining the prestige of the teaching profession and to fostering an educational environment that is fair, safe, and conducive to learning.

- Methodological Activity – A valuable teacher engages actively not only in the educational development of students but also in the life of the educational institution. This involvement extends beyond classroom teaching, contributing to the holistic development of students, the organization of extracurricular activities, educational projects, community partnerships, and initiatives aimed at institutional development. Additionally, it includes participation in working committees addressing the organizational and administrative dimensions of the profession. Such engagement reflects a vision of education as a complex process that transcends the boundaries of classroom instruction.

The teaching career is a structured and progressive professional pathway, defined by initial and continuous training, instructional and methodological activities, adherence to ethical and legal standards, and systematic evaluation. Its development requires ongoing professional growth and active engagement in both classroom and institutional life, ensuring the formation of competent, reflective, and adaptable educators capable of responding to the evolving demands of contemporary education.

2. The 2025 Educational Reforms in Romania: Implications for the Development of the Teaching Career

In 2025, educational reforms in Romania focused primarily on redefining and strengthening the teaching career as a key pillar in the modernization of the pre-university education system. Law No. 141 of 25 July 2025, concerning certain fiscal and budgetary measures, introduced significant changes in the educational system as part of a package of budget efficiency reforms for 2025 and 2026. In the context of an educational climate marked by legislative instability, a shortage of qualified personnel, and the declining attractiveness of the teaching profession, the promoted national policies indicate a paradigm shift in the teaching career. Consequently, the 2025 reforms, through the draft normative acts subsequent to the educational decisions under the aforementioned law, brought an increase in standards, responsibilities, and obligations for teachers. For educators, these regulations entail adaptation to new requirements regarding workload, professional training, and evaluation.

One of the main directions of the reform was the revision of professional standards for teachers, aimed at aligning the required competencies with the current needs of society and students. The new standards, developed in accordance with European trends and the strategies of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) regarding quality in education, emphasize digital competencies, critical thinking, educational inclusion, and student-centered learning.

In parallel, the teaching career pathway was restructured, recognizing diverse forms of professional development. The concept of a digital professional portfolio was introduced, gradually replacing traditional evaluation methods, allowing for continuous and personalized assessment of both teaching and methodological activities.

Furthermore, continuous professional development has become a strategic component in shaping the teaching career. In 2025, the focus shifted from simple courses or training programs to integrated professional development programs tailored to the actual needs of teachers. Digitalization has transformed the training process, providing teachers with access to personalized learning pathways.

The training program within the “Class of the Future – Digital Pedagogy” project, implemented by the Edu Apps Association in partnership with Babeş-Bolyai University Cluj-Napoca and the University of Bucharest, and supported by teaching staff from Teacher Training Houses in 11 cities, financed through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) and carried out during 2024 – 2026, is a modern educational initiative aimed at developing teachers’ professional competencies in integrating digital technologies into the instructional process. In the context of rapid societal changes and the accelerated digitalization of education, this program addresses the urgent need to adapt pedagogical practices to new teaching and learning paradigms.

The primary objective of the program is to develop digital teaching competencies in accordance with European standards (such as the DigCompEdu – Digital Competence Framework for Educators) and the requirements of the Romanian education system. The program approaches digital pedagogy not merely as technological use but as a set of innovative teaching strategies that leverage the potential of the digital environment to support active, differentiated, collaborative, and student-centered learning. Through its practical, flexible, and teacher-centered approach, the “Class of the Future – Digital Pedagogy” program (Edu Apps Association, 2024–2026) contributes to the modernization of the teaching career, supports the transformation of traditional schools into smart

learning spaces, and prepares teachers for the challenges and opportunities of future education.

Through Ministry of Education and Research Order (OMEC) No. 3986/05.05.2025, published in the Official Gazette No. 472 of 21 May 2025, the Framework Methodology regarding the types of programs for career development, quality assurance of programs, and the system for accumulating credits according to the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) for pre-university teachers was approved. According to this methodology, continuous professional development becomes both a right and an obligation for teachers in pre-university education.

The reform of the Romanian education system also aimed at increasing the attractiveness of the teaching profession. The teaching career seeks to regain its status as a vocation and a profession of prestige, and educational policies reflect a systemic, support- and development-oriented approach. The Ministry of Education maintains the National Register of Mentor Teachers in pre-university education, thereby providing support for novice teachers.

However, the implementation of these reforms faces significant challenges, such as chronic underfunding of education, resistance to change from certain institutional actors, the lack of a strong organizational culture in many educational institutions, and the gap between public policies and on-the-ground realities. The effectiveness of the reforms continues to depend on the system's capacity to ensure coherence, continuity, and tangible support for teachers at all stages of their career.

3. Approaches to the Professionalization of the Teaching Career in Romania

The professionalization of the teaching career represents a complex and dynamic process through which educational activity is recognized, consolidated,

and developed as a profession with clear standards of competence, responsibility, and autonomy. In the contemporary context of social, economic, and technological transformations, this process entails a shift from a traditional, knowledge-transmission-centered approach to a reflective and adaptive one, in which the teacher becomes a learning facilitator, cultural mediator, and agent of change.

The concept of “teacher professionalization” involves not only rigorous initial training but also the continuous development of professional, ethical, and personal competencies throughout the career. In this sense, professionalization requires following a structured pathway, accompanied by formal evaluation and recognition through the attainment of teaching ranks, certifications, and the adoption of professional values and responsibilities that go beyond the mere execution of a predefined role.

Starting with the 2020 – 2021 academic year, in eight universities in Romania, the project “Start in the Teaching Career through the Didactic Master’s Programme” was implemented. This project was initiated by the Ministry of Education and Research, approved for European funding under the Human Capital Operational Programme (POCU) 2014 – 2020, and subsequently regulated by Order of the Ministry of Education and Research (OMEC) No. 4524 of 12 June 2020 regarding the establishment and organization of university didactic master’s programmes.

The “Start in the Teaching Career through the Didactic Master’s Programme” project represented the cornerstone for the subsequent structuring and regulation of the didactic master’s programme within Romanian legislation and laid the foundations for a modern model of pedagogical training at the university level.

In the Higher Education Law No. 199/2023, the didactic master's programme was regulated as a system of initial professionalization for the teaching career, being structured either as an initial training programme of 90 credits or of 60 credits, depending on whether the psycho-pedagogical training programme had previously been completed within undergraduate degree programmes.

A key element in strengthening professionalization is the establishment of professional standards, which define the ideal teacher profile and serve as a reference for training, evaluation, and development. These standards are aligned with European key competencies for education and with good practice models proposed by international organizations such as the OECD or the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

In Romania, the professionalization of the teaching career is addressed through various strategic and legislative documents, including the Pre-university Education Law No. 198/2023, the previously mentioned Higher Education Law No. 199/2023 and Order No. 7386/11 November 2024 for the approval of the Professional Profile and Standards for Teachers in Pre-university Education.

The professionalization of the teaching career in Romania gained momentum with the implementation of the "Professionalization of the Teaching Career – PROF" project (Ministry of Education, 2021–2023). This strategic, nationally implemented initiative was co-financed by the European Social Fund through the Human Capital Operational Program (POCU) 2014–2020 and aimed to strengthen the system of initial and continuous teacher training in Romania, with a view to improving the quality of education and educational equity. Conducted between 2021 and 2023, the project focused on developing a teaching career framework based on a unified set of professional competencies and

differentiated training pathways tailored to the real needs of the system. Thus, emphasis was placed on professionalizing the teaching career through:

- Enhancement of Initial Teacher Education, through the support and modernization of study programs within teaching master's programs and psycho-pedagogical modules.
- Strengthening of Continuous Professional Development, by establishing local learning centers and developing the pedagogical, digital, and inclusion competencies of in-service teachers.
- Support for Teaching Practice and Mentorship, through partnerships between universities, schools, and other relevant institutions.
- Promotion of a Coherent Policy Framework for the Teaching Career, encompassing standards, evaluation mechanisms, and professional development pathways.

The project was coordinated by the Ministry of Education, in partnership with higher education institutions, teacher training centers, and other relevant organizations in the field of education. It targeted novice teachers, in-service teachers, as well as trainers and mentors within the pre-university and university education systems.

Within the PROF project, a Teacher's Guide was developed, contributing to the achievement of the project's overall objective: "to ensure professional mentorship throughout the entire teaching career in the pre-university education system, through the creation of a coherent and reliable national system for professional training and the development of teaching competencies, including psycho-pedagogical training necessary for occupying and performing teaching roles, as well as achieving pedagogical excellence in pre-university education, in teaching/ training activities and educational management, in the context of the global digitalization of education systems."

Additionally, the project addressed the specific objective of “continuous training and professional development aimed at career advancement and professional growth, ensuring pedagogical continuity in teaching-learning-assessment processes, with a particular focus on the practical teaching component (classroom instruction) of teacher training.” (Petrache et al., 2023)

4. Strategic Management of the Teaching Career: From Conceptual Frameworks to Implementation Planning

“The management of the teaching career is the process through which teachers plan, develop, and leverage their professional and personal competencies in order to achieve a coherent professional trajectory, adapted to both their own needs and those of the educational system.” (adapted from Manolescu, A., 2001; Pescaru, M., 2021)

This process aims to ensure a sustainable professional trajectory, as the teaching career is not perceived as a static path but as an ongoing professional construction, oriented towards performance, reflection, and adaptability.

The management of the teaching career is configured as a bidimensional process – individual and institutional – through which a balance is achieved between teachers’ professional aspirations and the strategic needs of the education system. It contributes not only to increasing professional efficiency but also to consolidating the identity and social status of the teaching profession, in accordance with the principles of lifelong learning.

- At the individual level, career management involves assuming responsibility for one’s own professional development through the identification of career goals, self-assessment of competencies, participation in continuous training programs, and leveraging accumulated pedagogical experience. The teacher thus becomes an active agent of their own professional growth, capable

of directing their trajectory according to interests, values, and available opportunities in the educational environment.

- At the institutional level, the management of the teaching career focuses on implementing policies and strategies that support the professional development of teaching staff through training programs, mentorship, evaluation, and motivation. Educational institutions are responsible for creating an environment conducive to professional growth, promoting performance, innovation, and engagement. In this context, alignment between organizational objectives (ensuring educational quality, adapting to change, professionalizing teaching staff) and individual teacher goals (self-development, stability, professional recognition) is pursued.

Planning the management of the teaching career represents the fundamental stage in teachers' professional development. It consists of the rational and anticipatory design of career development directions through the definition of professional objectives, training strategies, and specific self-development actions.

The process of planning a teaching career is carried out in several interdependent stages, each aimed at guiding and optimizing professional development:

1. **Professional Self-Assessment.** At this stage, the teacher analyzes their competencies, values, interests, and motivations. Strengths and areas for improvement are identified, establishing the basis for a realistic and personalized plan.

2. **Setting Career Objectives.** This involves clearly defining professional goals, such as obtaining teaching ranks, participating in continuous professional development programs, engaging in educational projects, conducting research activities, or assuming leadership and mentorship roles.

3. Developing the Professional Development Plan. This stage involves selecting strategies, resources, and activities necessary to achieve the established objectives. The teacher outlines their professional trajectory, establishing deadlines and criteria for evaluating progress.

4. Implementing the Plan. This stage involves the concrete application of the planned actions (participation in training, engagement in innovative teaching activities, collaboration in educational teams, etc.).

5. Monitoring and Evaluating Progress. This involves analyzing achieved results, adjusting objectives, and redefining strategies in response to changes in the professional and institutional environment.

5. Conclusions

The teaching career is a structured, progressive, and multifaceted professional pathway, encompassing initial and continuous training, instructional and methodological activities, ethical and legal responsibilities, and systematic evaluation. The professionalization and management of the teaching career are essential for ensuring the development of competent, reflective, and adaptable educators capable of responding to the evolving demands of contemporary education.

Educational reforms in Romania, particularly those implemented in 2025, emphasized the modernization of the teaching profession, the integration of digital competencies, mentorship, and coherent career planning. Programs such as “Class of the Future – Digital Pedagogy” and the PROF project demonstrate the strategic approach to professional development, combining individual responsibility with institutional support.

Effective career management involves a balance between individual aspirations and systemic needs, structured planning, continuous monitoring, and adaptive strategies. Ultimately, the sustainable development of the teaching

career contributes not only to educational quality and innovation but also to the recognition and prestige of the teaching profession, fostering a culture of lifelong learning and professional excellence.

The management of the teaching career can be analyzed from the perspective of the continuous professional development of teachers, as an essential dimension of the professionalization and sustainable development of the profession. Scientific research in this field contributes to the identification and conceptualization of key competencies in teaching career management, such as planning and self-regulation of the professional pathway, critical reflection on educational practice, adaptability to systemic changes, mentoring, and the integration of digital technologies into the professional development process. Integrating these competencies into a coherent and sustainable training pathway enables the theoretical and methodological grounding of an appropriate continuing education curriculum, aligned both with the real needs of teachers and with the current demands of the educational system. In this context, a curriculum developed on the basis of research findings supports the continuous professionalization of teachers, contributes to improving the quality of the educational process, and facilitates alignment between teachers' individual aspirations and national education policies.

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